

GENDER CRITERIA IN EDUCATION AND THEIR PEDAGOGICAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL CONTENT

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Abstract: This article highlights the need to familiarize future teachers with the theoretical and methodological foundations of gender pedagogy and psychology, the development of skills and competencies related to the implementation of the gender approach in psychological and pedagogical knowledge in educators, the development of the concept of the continuous introduction of gender education at all stages of education and the problems of ensuring.

Kalit soʻzlar: taʼlim, gender, gender tenglik, gender yondashuv, xotin-qizlar, ehtiyoj, muhofaza, gender va inson, taʼlim va gender.

Ключевые слова: образование, гендер, гендерное равенство, гендерный подход, женщины, потребности, защита, гендер и человек, образование и гендер.

Key words: education, gender, gender equality, gender approach, women, need, protection, gender and man, education and gender.

Introduction Nowadays, when fundamental changes are taking place in the socio-economic, spiritual-intellectual life of Uzbekistan, the issue of organizing the educational process on the basis of gender equality and differences of the individual should become a component of the pedagogical process and research. After all, the regulation of social and educational relations between girls and boys has an important pedagogical value. Because social relations between male and female members of society will be decided in the future through educational processes.[1]

In our country, only at the end of the 20th century, ideas about taking into account gender differences and similarities in the educational process began to be put forward. Gender differences and similarities are based on taking into account the similarities and differences in the educational activities of girls and boys in the educational process. This, in turn, helps ensure the effectiveness of the educational process. Belonging to one or another gender determines the capabilities of the student.

The Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan establishes the legal basis for ensuring gender equality in the education system. On the basis of the Law "On Education" adopted in 2020, the equal rights of boys and girls studying in all educational institutions and choosing a profession are ensured.[2]

The reforms carried out in our republic are giving positive results in the economic, social, political, cultural and educational aspects of our society. Such changes are consistently implemented in the education system, as in all areas.

Our observations showed that the problems of forming general labor skills among students based on gender equality and differences have not been studied in labor classes of general secondary schools. One of the main reasons for this is that the educational content and educational process are not implemented taking into account gender, that is, sexual, physical, mental differences, interests and aspirations, and physiological characteristics between boys and girls. This is the most important factor that determines the relevance of the problem we have chosen as a research topic. One of the important aspects of the research is that the concept of gender is interpreted as a socio-pedagogical gender, that is, the student as a subject of the educational process is differentiated in a gender way in a socio-pedagogical sense.

In the 21st century, continuous education has gained strategic importance and occupies a key position in the life of individuals and society. A person can master continuous technological innovations only with the help of the knowledge obtained in the educational process organized with gender equality and identity in mind. This requires not only the improvement of labor tools, but also the ability to acquire new knowledge and thorough mastering of professional activities.

In the educational process, gender is expressed through a specific basis of socialization, division of labor and cultural norms accepted in society, types of social activities, and their social status. The gender norms and criteria adopted in the educational system serve to determine to a certain extent the mental qualities, abilities, types of activities, occupations of students, depending on their biological sex. In the process of education, teachers, family, school, environment together inculcate gender norms and criteria in the minds of students. These views create the basis for students to have their first ideas about what a real woman and a real man should be. Later, these gender norms are strengthened through the types of activities formed in students.

Methods Gender socialization in the educational process is the process of assimilation of the gender cultural system of the society in which the student lives. As important signs of gender socialization in the educational process, it is to direct students to the profession, to distribute the educational work correctly, and to determine personal qualities based on gender characteristics in them.

The institution of education, along with other agents of socialization, determines gender identity, and in this regard, people have the opportunity to make personal, civic and professional choices. This process is not clear or deliberate (namerenny) goal, but educational institutions provide effective lessons of gender relations. Educators have highlighted a number of approaches to gender analysis of education or hidden curriculum analysis. (hidden curriculum is copied from the English term). This is, first of all, the institution itself, including gender relations at work, gender stratification (stratification) of the teaching profession. Secondly, it includes the content of subjects and thirdly, the teaching method. These three dimensions of the hidden curriculum not only reflect gender stereotypes in the process of socialization, but also support gender inequality. Let's take a closer look at the manifestation of the hidden curriculum.

1. Characteristics of the social structure of the higher educational institution. Educational institutions reflect the gender stratification of society and culture in general, which demonstrates the unequal status of women and men: as a rule, teachers, secretaries and staff are women, and the school director or university rector is a man.

90% of the teaching staff of primary and secondary educational institutions are women, and as the status of the educational institution increases (from kindergarten to university), the number of female teachers decreases. In general, while modern Russia is characterized by the feminization of higher education and science, today among university professors there are men (in a number of higher education institutions, for example, the number of men does not exceed 20%), the low-paid staff of scientific laboratories consists almost entirely of women. At the same time, the basic average salary of male teachers is 35% higher than the average salary of female teachers.[3]

Women-led educational institutions are a very important source of identity. Russian researchers noted that among schoolchildren, our compatriots consider mathematics, physics, physical education, and computer knowledge to be the most important for boys, and for girls, home economics, literature and history, ethics and psychology of family life, sexual education. Thus, gender-based career choice is programmed. In addition, stereotypes of women's and men's homework are established in labor lessons in schools and educational institutions. Future teachers take on appropriate roles not only in their families, but also in pedagogical universities.[4]

2. Composition of subjects. The stereotypical image of men as active and successful norms and women as "invisible" (women simply do not exist, dropped in the presentation) or invisible, inactive and dependent learning materials and medium and [4] and is being reproduced in specialized resources used for teaching at the higher education level.[5]

The consequences of this misrepresentation of women in educational materials are as follows. First, students may conclude that it is men who are the standard and who play the most important roles in society and culture. Second, students have limited knowledge of how women have contributed to culture, as well as areas of our lives that are traditionally considered feminine. Third, at the individual level, curriculum stereotypes encourage male achievement, while females learn behavioral patterns unrelated to leadership and management.

3. Communication processes. The teaching style, forms of relationships in the educational audience affect the gender socialization of students, and often women's ways of acquiring knowledge and expressing themselves are not highly valued. In 1982, in the USA, R. Hall and B. Sandler were the first to conduct a study of verbal (verbal) and non-verbal (non-verbal) communication practices in education. This research has become a classic example of similar projects carried out in schools and colleges, in adult educational examinations and universities.

Results Kindergarten teachers and school teachers continue the family's efforts to form different behaviors in girls and boys: it is noted that shouting from the seat, minor indiscipline by girls, leads to active rejection of teachers, and children are left out of the "attention" of the same actions. Girls are forced under great pressure by teachers and parents to unquestioningly obey all norms, rules and customs. Boys are allowed to deviate from the norms of behavior, thus encouraging their research activities, and girls are prohibited from doing so.

Differences in the attitude of teachers towards students of different genders are more clearly manifested in gifted children and adolescents. Therefore, teachers believe that gifted boys are superior to their classmates in critical and logical thinking and creative problem solving. Male teachers perceive gifted students more traditionally than female teachers, that

is, they perceive them as more emotional, meek, trusting, less imaginative, curious and intelligent. In addition, it was found that teachers give low grades to female students who demonstrate the ability to think analytically, put forward their original ideas, and resist traditional conventions. 'girls have a high rating among teachers.[6] A similar practice of cooperation continues at the level of university education.

Discussion The hidden curriculum is defined as the language of social control with metacommunication. First, these teachers allow boys to show themselves and express their activity; girls are encouraged to obey and have a beautiful appearance; more individual classes are held with boys, more time is devoted to them than girls.[7] In addition, dominant forms of teaching rely on male communication methods. For example, quizzes, individual reports, and grading competitions are encouraged as "bravery." Both girls and boys suffer because neither of them develop critical thinking skills, questioning, group discussion and problem solving.[8]

Conclusion For example, the existence of gender stereotypes about the abilities and educational preferences of women and men also affects the dissemination of research results. New opportunities for women and men, the principles of gender equality in education reflect reflexive play and freedom in the field of space, where they are freed from drill, aggression and "hand training" and other things. gentleness, grace and respect can be exercised instead. The student and the teacher work as partners who plan changes together and proactively, monitor progress and evaluate the quality of what has been achieved, openly discuss misunderstandings and find ways to resolve them. Therefore, the organization of the educational process itself includes openness and flexibility, experiments and alternative solutions in addition to traditional experiences.

References:

1. Тилавова М.М. Гендер тенглик ва фарқлар асосида ўқувчи фаолиятини ривожлантириш имкониятлари. Тошкент, 2010. – Б. 5. (- 121 б.)
2. Ўзбекистон Республикасининг Қонуни, 23.09.2020 йилдаги ЎРҚ-637-сон. <https://lex.uz/docs/5013007>
3. Горшкова И., Беляева Г. Профессиональное самочувствие женских научно-педагогических кадров МГУ (Результаты опроса 1998 года) // Женщина. Гендер. Культура. М., 1999. С. 194–207.
4. Воронина О. А. Права женщин в сфере образования // Права женщин в России: исследование реальной практики их соблюдения и массового сознания: в 2 т. Т. 1. М., 1998. С. 301–305.
5. Барчунова Т. Сексизм в букваре // ЭКО. Новосибирск. 1995. № 3.
6. Гендерная экспертиза учебников для высшей школы / под ред. О. А. Ворониной. М., 2005. 260 с.
7. Попова Л.В. Гендерные аспекты самореализации личности: учеб. пособие к спецсеминару. М., 1996. С. 17–18.
8. Словарь гендерных терминов / под ред. А. А. Денисовой. М., 2002. С. 47–48.